

NEW DEVELOPMENTS IN ONSET THEORY FOR ONSET OF RESIN FAILURE IN FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

This paper presents recent work on the Strain Invariant Failure Theory (SIFT) that has recently been named Onset Theory to emphasise its application to onset of irreversible damage in carbon fibre and glassy polymeric resins. The theory was first proposed by Gosse and Christensen [1]. It is based on two fundamental assertions; that prediction of failure of homogeneous materials should be based on strain, and that the onset of irreversible behaviour in homogeneous solids arises from only two possible modes. In the case of glassy polymer resins, failure can occur via excessive dilatation (volume change) or excessive distortion (shape change). Only two intrinsic material properties are required to characterise these failures, based on the first strain invariant (dilatation) and the second deviatoric strain invariant.

In the approach defined by Pipes and Gosse [2], laminate strains are dehomogenised to give representative strains in the composite constituents using enhancement factors derived from the micromechanical analysis of fibre-matrix unit cells. Critical values are defined for the dilatational and distortional invariants for the resin using 90 degree and 10 degree unidirectional off-axis test specimens respectively.

Critically, validation of the theory has been provided by Sul et al. [3] by reproducing the failure modes in molecular dynamics simulations completely independently of experimentally derived approach of Pipes and Gosse. Recent developments include refinements of the testing procedures that are used to define the critical invariants and the use of submodelling to dehomogenise the strains.

The research has shown that the shear-bending coupling that occurs in the off-axis specimens can be alleviated by using high aspect ratio 14:1 specimens and bonding tabs to the specimens so that failures initiate outside the grips. Unidirectional specimens are used because the onset of damage and final failure occur at the same test strain. The invariants are then sampled on the actual failure surface in the finite element analysis used to back out the critical invariants.

In the recent work [4-6] the use of enhancement factors (previously strain amplification factors) to dehomogenise the strains is validated by a micromechanical submodelling approach. This method embedded micromechanical models within the simulation domain such that critical strains in the constituents could be directly extracted from one simulation. The benefit of the direct micromechanical approach is most apparent for preliminary studies which may cover a variety of material options and/or sensitivity and parameter studies. In these cases the direct approach is more computationally efficient as it removes the computational repetition required to construct the enhancement factor matrix [7].

In this paper the application of Onset Theory to specimens manufactured from plain weave fabric plies will be described. The approach involves two levels of dehomogenisation – from the laminate to individual tows in the fabric plies, and then from the tows to strains in the fibre and resin at the fibre level. The development of an approach to characterise the growth of the damage into micro-cracks and failure at the laminate level will be briefly introduced.

2 Review of the Onset Theory

2.1 Strain Invariants

Onset Theory is a recent development for glassy polymers constrained by fibres in structural composites. The theory simply posits that the constrained polymer will fail when subjected to excessive deformation; either through excessive volume change (dilatation) or excessive shape change (distortion). This fundamental property of polymer materials is based heavily in thermodynamic theory and has been confirmed by atomistic simulation of polymers [3].

To quantify dilatation and distortion, strain invariants are used, related to the fundamental invariants of the strain tensor. The dilatational invariant is equal to the first strain invariant, J_1 , and is shown in Equation 1. The distortional invariant is equal to the square root of the second deviatoric strain invariant, J_2' , and is shown in Equation 2.

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{dil} &= \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \\ &= \varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_y + \varepsilon_z\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{dis} &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{6} \left[\begin{aligned} &(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)^2 \\ &+(\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3)^2 \\ &+(\varepsilon_3 - \varepsilon_1)^2 \end{aligned} \right]} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{6} \left[\begin{aligned} &(\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y)^2 \\ &+(\varepsilon_y - \varepsilon_z)^2 \\ &+(\varepsilon_z - \varepsilon_x)^2 \end{aligned} \right]} + \frac{1}{4} \left[\begin{aligned} &\gamma_{xy}^2 \\ &+\gamma_{yz}^2 \\ &+\gamma_{zx}^2 \end{aligned} \right]}\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where:

ε_{dil} = Dilatational strain invariant

ε_{dis} = Distortional strain invariant

$\varepsilon_{1,2,3}$ = Principal elastic strains

$\varepsilon_{x,y,z}$ = Engineering elastic strain

$\gamma_{xy,yz,zx}$ = tensor in Cartesian coordinates

Irreversible behaviour is predicted to occur when either the dilatational or distortional strain invariant at any location in the resin exceeds the

corresponding critical value, $\varepsilon_{dil,crit}$ or $\varepsilon_{dis,crit}$. The two critical strain invariants are considered intrinsic material properties.

2.2 Effect of Temperature

Onset theory explicitly accounts for the thermal residual strains present in constrained resin by only evaluating strain invariants using *elastic* strains; those which are compatible with the stress tensor through Hooke's Law, as shown in Equation 3.

$$\varepsilon_i = S_{ij} \sigma_j \quad (3)$$

For a fully constrained 3D element of resin subjected to a positive temperature increment, ΔT , the principal elastic strains are given by Equation 4.

$$\varepsilon_{1,2,3} = -\alpha \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where:

α = Linear coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) for the resin

Therefore, strain due to the thermal shrinkage of free resin does not lead to failure. On the other hand, shrinkage of constrained resin, such as that constrained by fibres, leads to a non-zero elastic strain tensor, which can lead to failure. All strain tensor terms shown in this paper are taken from the elastic strain tensor.

2.3 Dehomogenisation

An important feature of the onset theory is the dehomogenisation process of the composite structure. This allows determination of the components of the strain tensor field within the matrix phase and fibre phase [2] and enables damage prediction within a complex structural domain, such as the random distribution of fibres and resin shown in Fig. 1 (a). With this process, the thermal residual effect due to the thermal contraction mismatch of fibre and resin is also taken into account.

Two Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) are used to account for the distribution of fibres and resin within the composite, shown in Fig. 1 (b). The justification and validation of this approach is given in [7].

Fig. 1. (a) Realistic distribution of fibres and resin within a composite and (b) Idealised Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) with the same volume fraction (V_f).

A series of critical points, k , are used as sampling points within the RVE. At each point a matrix of *enhancement factors*, \mathbf{M}_{ij}^k , is generated which relates the internal strain tensor term, i , to the externally applied unit strain tensor term, j . A thermal strain vector, \mathbf{A}_i^k , relates the internal strain tensor term, i , to a unit temperature differential applied to the model.

Algorithmically, the dehomogenisation process can be expressed for laminates made from unidirectional plies as follows:

1. Analyse a continuum model with mechanical load to define the elastic strains, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^M$, in the plies.
2. Analyse the continuum model with free boundaries but $\Delta T = T - T_{cure}$ to define the elastic strains, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T$, in the plies due to the cure process.
3. Superimpose the elastic strains, apply the strain enhancement factors and add the cure strains due to the fibre and resin mismatch, as shown in Equation 5.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^k = \mathbf{M}_{ij}^k (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j^M + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j^T) + \mathbf{A}_i^k \Delta T \quad (5)$$

where:

$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^k$ = Micro-elastic strain tensor at the k^{th} point in the RVE

\mathbf{M}_{ij}^k = Enhancement matrix for the k^{th} point in the RVE

\mathbf{A}_i^k = Thermal strain vector due to CTE mismatch between the fibre and resin at the k^{th} point in the RVE

ΔT = Thermal difference between service temperature and cure temperature

With the aid of micromechanical enhancement, a detailed assessment of irreversible deformation is possible beyond the homogenous deformation state [2, 7]. Damage onset within the matrix phase is predicted when Equation 6 is satisfied.

$$\max \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{dil}}{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{dil,crit}}, \frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{dis}}{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{dis,crit}} \right) \geq 1 \quad (6)$$

Damage onset within the fibre phase is not addressed in this paper.

3 Evaluation of Critical Strain Invariants for Resin Failure

As was summarised in the previous section, the onset of the matrix/resin failure can be conducted when the critical dilatational and distortional strain invariants are known. As the deformation of the matrix in real unidirectional laminates is constrained by the fibres, the ideal method is to achieve the constrained strain state in a neat resin test and extract the critical strain invariants. However, this is a difficult problem and is still under investigation.

An alternative approach has been adopted to extract the critical invariants for the resin failure that was by using unidirectional composite tensile tests and then their corresponding finite element analysis. A set of different off-axis unidirectional tests from 10° to 90° to generate critical values of strain invariants for the matrix has been proposed by Pipes and Gosse [2]. The 0° specimen was omitted as it will fail in the fibres. Based on these tests and normalised distortional and dilatational invariants, 10° specimen

provides the critical invariant for distortional behaviour while the 90° specimen determines the critical invariant for dilatational deformation. This approach was successfully applied by Tran et al. [6] on a different material and was able to determine the onset of resin failure of the material.

In this paper, the critical invariants required for the fabric architectures and damage progression in the subsequent sections was based on T800s/3900-2 specimens. The dimensions of the specimens are 252 mm length, 19.05 mm width and 5.8 mm thickness. In this evaluation, only 10° and 90° specimens were utilised for the off-axis uniaxial tensile tests. A MTS810 uniaxial hydraulic testing machine with capacity of 100 kN was utilised with surfalloy wedges to reduce specimen failure in the grips section. Material properties of T800s/3900-2 are given in Table 1 and were applied in the finite element analysis to determine the critical strain invariants.

Table 1. Material properties of T800s fibre and 3900-2 resin with fibre volume fraction=60%.

Properties	T800s	3900-2
E_1 (GPa)	303	3.3
E_2 (GPa)	15.2	3.3
E_3 (GPa)	15.2	3.3
G_{12} (GPa)	9.65	1.22
G_{23} (GPa)	6.32	1.22
G_{13} (GPa)	9.65	1.22
ν_{12}	0.2	0.35
ν_{23}	0.2	0.35
ν_{13}	0.2	0.35
α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	0	57.6×10^{-6}
$\alpha_{22} = \alpha_{33}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	8.3×10^{-6}	57.6×10^{-6}

The critical dilatational and distortional strain invariants were found to be 22500 $\mu\epsilon$ and 119000 $\mu\epsilon$ respectively.

4 Fabric Architectures

4.1 Fabric Modelling

The new work in this paper includes an extension of onset theory to fabric architectures. Continuum laminate strains are dehomogenised to define local strains in the tow architecture of the fabric. This will be achieved using meso-mechanical RVE cell analysis in which the resin and tows are modelled as continua, as shown in Fig. 2. In this paper, the

materials applied for the tows and resin are T300/3900-2 lamina and 3900-2 epoxy respectively and their corresponding material properties are given in Table 2.

Fig. 2. (a) RVE cell, (b) tow and (c) resin part of the meso-mechanical unit cell model for strain dehomogenisation.

Table 2. Material properties of T300/3900-2 lamina for tows and 3900-2 for resin.

Properties	T300/3900-2 lamina	3900-2 Epoxy resin
E_1 (GPa)	135	3.3
E_2 (GPa)	8	3.3
E_3 (GPa)	8	3.3
G_{12} (GPa)	5	1.22
G_{23} (GPa)	2.76	1.22
G_{13} (GPa)	5	1.22
ν_{12}	0.25	0.35
ν_{23}	0.44	0.35
ν_{13}	0.25	0.35
α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	1.05×10^{-7}	57.6×10^{-6}
$\alpha_{22} = \alpha_{33}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	32×10^{-6}	57.6×10^{-6}

The material properties were applied along the local axis of the tows to retain the accurate orthotropic behaviour during the cell analysis. The volume fraction of the tows to the unit cell is 55.62%. The dimensions of the unit cell are 1.363 mm length, 1.363 mm width and 0.25 mm height to represent one layer thickness. The tow's major and minor axis ratio is set to be 12:1, where the minor axis diameter is 0.1 mm. In the experimental tensile test conducted in this project for this material, the failure strain was 1.3%. This strain was applied perpendicular to the surface perpendicular to x-axis. The other surfaces were constrained to remain planar with no net normal reaction force to represent symmetric free contraction boundaries.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the contour plots of dilatational and distortional invariants of the unit cell model respectively, where these results were represented using the separate tows and resin entities. The maximum dilatational and distortional invariants were located along the slender edge of the transverse tows. The maximum dilatational invariant was 26488 $\mu\epsilon$ and occurred directly adjacent to the large resin volume in the centre of the model. Meanwhile, the maximum distortional invariant was 25854 $\mu\epsilon$ and was located in the region where the tows overlapped each other. In the tows, the maximum dilatational invariant was near the centre region of the RVE cell while the maximum distortional invariant was located within the bulk of the transverse tows in the overlapping region.

These critical locations in the RVE cell were dehomogenised and the maximum dilatational

invariant was found to be 41500 $\mu\epsilon$ and the maximum distortional invariant was 40500 $\mu\epsilon$. In this case failure is predicted to occur through dilatation within the transverse tow volume. This agrees with existing evidence for the location of micro-cracking in fabrics however a direct comparison predicted failure strain has not been attempted.

Fig. 3. Dilatational invariant of the RVE cell model with (a) tows and (b) resin entities.

Fig. 4. Distortional invariant of the RVE cell model with (a) tows and (b) resin entities.

4.2 Fabric Dehomogenisation Process

A bi-level fabric dehomogenisation process is proposed for fabric modelling. The continuum strains will be dehomogenised using fabric RVE models with continuum tow material. The tow material will be further dehomogenised using RVE models of UD material.

Fig. 5. Two level dehomogenisation required to apply onset theory to fabric parts

The link between the length scales can be achieved with embedded submodels however this is computationally very inefficient. The methodology proposed here is to extend the Onset Theory approach to UD materials, which uses enhancement factors at chosen critical locations.

The new formulation for the strain within the tow will be given by Equation 6.

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_i^{kl} = \mathbf{M}_{ij}^k (\mathbf{M}_{ij}^l \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_j + \mathbf{A}^l \Delta T) + \mathbf{A}^k \Delta T \quad (7)$$

where all symbols have their previous meaning with k representing a selected critical sampling point within the UD RVE model and l representing a selected critical point within the tows of the fabric RVE model.

This formulation is under development and has not yet been tested. A key challenge is the selection of critical locations in the fabric unit cell which will capture the majority of critical strain cases for an arbitrary continuum strain, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_j$.

5 Damage Progression

A damage progression algorithm based on Onset Theory and an element elimination method has been developed by Tay et al [8]. A similar algorithm is being developed here using a sub-model embedded in a global analysis as shown in Fig. 6. The sub-model is a microscopic three-dimensional fibre-resin model that attempts to follow the growth of damage following initiation at the micro-mechanical level predicted by the strain invariants. Displacements from the global analysis are applied to the boundaries of the sub-model.

Fig. 6 Three-dimensional submodel for damage progression.

The algorithm evaluates the dilatational and distortional invariants at the centre of each element. The properties in elements that have exceeded the critical values are reduced before returning to repeat the analysis. If the damage coalesces into a micro-crack the growth can be contained by the fibre architecture. The algorithm also evaluates the strain energy release rate in order to provide a measure that can be used to limit the growth of cracks that are not constrained by the fibres.

The algorithm has been applied to follow the history of damage developing in a specimen manufacture from T800/3900-2 unidirectional tape with the layout $0_2/90_4/0_2$. This problem has been investigated by several authors, the paper by Nairn [9] being typical of the work that has been done. The analysis predicts that under axial load transverse cracks will develop in the 90° layers that will exhibit a characteristic spacing. The axial strain shown in Fig. 7(a) is relieved by the presence of the crack and there is a gap before the strain is restored to pre-crack levels by the requirement for compatibility with the 0° layer. Experimental results indicate that cracks first appear in the 90° plies at an average axial strain of $5000\mu\epsilon$. At higher strains intermediate cracks appear until the spacing reduces to an average spacing of about 1 to 1.5 times the thickness of the central 90° tow region as shown in Fig. 7(b).

Application of the new algorithm showed no initiation of microcracks (the dilatational invariant was everywhere less than the critical value) for an average axial strain of $4500\mu\epsilon$. The first crack appeared for an axial strain of $5000\mu\epsilon$. The crack growth extended across the width of the 90° plies and arrested (the dilatational invariant fell below the critical value) on the boundary with the 0° plies. The submodel was then moved so that the initial crack was on the left-hand boundary. A second crack initiated at $6000\mu\epsilon$, extended across the 90° plies and again arrested. A third crack formed mid-way between the first two cracks when the average axial strain was raised to above $7000\mu\epsilon$. No further crack initiation occurred even though the axial strain was raised to the average strain for two-piece failure of the specimen.

The Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image in Fig. 8 also reveals that the cracks grow on the interface with the fibre and finger shaped

microscopic cavitations can grow in the resin perpendicular to the fibre axis. These finger cracks then coalesce into the primary fracture surface extending parallel to the fibre axis.

The new algorithm is being applied to a refined model of fibre and resin to investigate this initial phase of crack growth. Initial results indicate the damage grows on the surface of the fibre parallel to the final fracture surface before bridging the gap between the fibres across a bridge that could be interpreted as leading to a finger crack.

(a)

(b)

Fig 7. (a) Axial strain distribution leading to cracks and (b) equally spaced transverse cracks in $0_2/90_4/0_2$ T800/3900-2 tape specimen.

Fig. 8. Damage growth at a microscopic level. SEM image of finger cracks near surface of a T300/Cycom970 specimen.

6 Conclusion

Onset Theory for the prediction of the onset of failure in unidirectional composite laminates has been well established. This paper extends the application of Onset Theory to the prediction of damage initiation sites in composite fabrics and also the micro/macroscale progression of damage within a heterogeneous fibre-resin system.

The application to laminates manufactured from fabric plies required two levels of dehomogenisation. The first from the laminate to the fabric tow will depend on the architecture of the fabric with different unit cell models required for plane weave and satin weave, for example. The second level of dehomogenisation to the fibre/resin level requires the properties of the fibre and resin and includes the fibre volume fraction of the fibre in the fabric tow. Future work will involve an experimental investigation of damage development in fabric specimens that will permit the location and strain levels, at which the microcracks develop, to be compared with the theoretical predictions.

The work on damage progression is new and the current methodology is intended to predict the initial growth of the damage. A methodology will need to be developed to create a crack in the global model following the development of damage at the microscopic level to allow the simulation to be extended to the laminate level.

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